

THE COMBINED EFFECT OF RICHARDSON EXTRAPOLATION AND θ -METHOD
IN STABILITY FOR SOLVING IVP

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Abstract

Richardson extrapolation method along with θ -method is an accelerating method to find a solution of initial value problems. In this study we have discussed several well-known stability definitions, and also the combined effect of Richardson extrapolation and θ - method on the stability of solving ODEs numerically. θ - method is stable on the origin and the method is stable on negative real axis ($\alpha < 0$) and for positive real axis on $2 < \alpha$ for $\theta \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$ and it is stable on the imaginary axis for all $\theta \in [0.5, 1]$ but it is unstable for $\theta \in [0, 0.5)$

Key words: Richardson extrapolation (RE), Initial value problems (IVP), Ordinary differential equation (ODE), Truncation Error (TE)

1. Introduction

Initial value problems are frequently occurring in mathematical models that arise in many branches of science, engineering and economics. Unfortunately it is seldom that these equations have solutions which can be expressed in closed form, so it is common to seek approximate solutions by means of numerical methods. Nowadays this can usually be achieved very inexpensively to high accuracy and with a reliable bound on the error between the analytical solution and its numerical approximation [1].

Extrapolation is the practice of estimating the truncation error of the numerical solution to an initial value problem, and using this error to bring the numerical solution to a value closer to that of the analytical exact solution [2].

Richardson extrapolation is an accelerating method to improve the rate of convergence of a sequence of solutions. It is named after Lewis Fry Richardson, who introduced the technique in the early 20th century [3], which can successfully be used in the efforts to improve the accuracy of the approximate solutions of systems of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) obtained by different numerical methods [4].

Many texts (journals and books) were published by applying Richardson extrapolation on different area of mathematics such as; two-dimensional Laplace equation using triangular and square grids [5], Finite difference methods [6], Eigenvalue approximations for second order elliptic problems by the mixed finite element method [7], boundary value problems for differential equations with irregular right-hand side [8], improve the convergence of explicit Runge–kutta method [4], Romberg integration and differentiation [9] and numerical solution of ordinary and

partial differential equations [2, 4, 10]. Richardson extrapolation does not depend too much on the particular numerical method to solve initial value problems [4].

It can be used numerical methods such as Runge kutta 2nd and 4th, Euler's forward and backward, θ -method, Adam's-moulton etc [11]. θ -Method is the single step method used to find the solution of initial value problems.

Therefore, in this study initial value problems have been solved by using Richardson extrapolation method together with θ -method and stability interval was investigated.

2. Richardson extrapolation Method

Due to wide application of Richardson extrapolation method different attempts have been made to solve some practical problems in science and engineering. Let us consider the classical initial value problem for systems of $s(s \geq 1)$ ordinary differential equations.

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = f(t, y), \quad t \in [a, b], \quad a < b, \quad f(a) = y_0 \quad (1)$$

Where, the unknown function $y: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}^s$ is continuously differentiable, while right-hand-side function $f(t, y)$ is continuous. However, it is often necessary to introduce much more restrictive assumptions when numerical methods of order p such as Runge - Kutta 2nd and 4th, Euler's forward and backward, θ -method, Adam's-moulton are used in the treatment of (1).

In such cases it is necessary to assume that the function y is continuously differentiable up to order p .

Richardson Extrapolation can be introduced in the following way. Assume that $t_n \in [a, b]$ is a time-point and given that $y(t_n)$ is the value of the exact solution of (1) at $t = t_n$. Assume also that two approximations of $y(t_n)$ have been obtained by applying the above numerical methods of order p and by using two time-step sizes h and $0.5h$. More precisely, starting from a time-point (grid point) $t = t_{n-1}$ where $t_{n-1} = t_n - h$, the two approximations are calculated by using first one large time-step and, after that, two small time-steps. Denoting these two approximations with z_n and w_n respectively, we can write:

$$y(t_n) = z_n + h^p k + o(h^{(p+1)}) \quad (2)$$

$$y(t_n) = w_n + \left(\frac{h}{2}\right)^p k + o(h^{p+1}) \quad (3)$$

Where k is some quantity depending on the numerical method applied in the calculation of z_n and w_n but not on the step size h . To solve this system of equation multiply equation (3) by

$$2^p \text{ gives } 2^p y(t_n) = 2^p w_n + h^p k + o(h^{p+1}) \quad (4)$$

Subtracting equation (2) from equation (4) gives

$$y(t_n) = \frac{2^p w_n - z_n}{2^p - 1} + o(h^{p+1})$$

$$\text{Define } y_n = \frac{2^p w_n - z_n}{2^p - 1} \quad (5)$$

It is clear that the approximation y_n being of order h^{p+1} , will in general be more accurate than both z_n and w_n (at least the step size h is sufficiently small) [10]. Thus, Richardson Extrapolation can be used in the efforts to improve the accuracy of the approximate solution. There are two ways of implementing the Richardson Extrapolation. These are active (can updates the solution at each successive steps) and passive (can't updates the solution at each successive steps) [4].

3. θ -method

This is one of the numerical methods used to solve ordinary differential equations with the general formula of $y_{n+1} = y_n + h[(1-\theta)f(t_n, y_n) + \theta f(t_{n+1}, y_{n+1})]$, $\theta \in [0,1]$ (6)

All properties of θ -Method for $\theta=0$, $\theta=0.5$ and $\theta=1$ are the properties of Euler's forward method, Trapezoidal Rule and Euler's Backward method respectively.

A. Forward Euler's method

Euler's method is one of the single step method expressed as $y_{n+1} = y_n + hf(t_n, y_n)$, where h is the step size. According to this equation the slope estimate f is used to extrapolate from an old value y_n to a new value y_{n+1} over a distance h [9]. The order of Euler's method is one.

B. Backward Euler's method

The order of Euler's backward method is one; it is special cases of θ -Method for $\theta=1$ expressed as $y_{n+1} = y_n + hf(t_{n+1}, y_{n+1})$.

C. Trapezoidal Rule

The only method of order two in θ -Method is trapezoidal rule; it is special cases of θ -Method for $\theta=0.5$. it can be expressed as $y_{n+1} = y_n + \frac{h}{2}[f(t_n, y_n) + f(t_{n+1}, y_{n+1})]$

4. Combining the Richardson Extrapolation method with θ -method

Let h be the large step size then using equation (6) perform two small time steps

$$w_{n-0.5} = y_{n-1} + 0.5h[(1-\theta)f(t_{n-1}, y_{n-1}) + \theta f(t_{n-0.5}, y_{n-0.5})] \quad (7)$$

$$w_n = w_{n-0.5} + 0.5h[(1-\theta)f(t_{n-0.5}, w_{n-0.5}) + \theta f(t_n, w_n)] \quad (8)$$

Since the order of θ -method for $\theta=0.5$ is 2 and for $\theta \neq 0.5$ the method is order of one then the general formula of combination of Richardson extrapolation with θ -method is

$$y_n = \frac{4w_n - z_n}{3} \text{ and } y_n = 2w_n - z_n \text{ for } \theta = 0.5 \text{ and for } \theta \neq 0.5 \text{ respectively}$$

5. Stability analysis

Several well-known stability definitions are relevant when classical systems of ODEs are solved numerically [4], some of them will be used in the remaining part of this paper.

Consider the famous linear test equation $y' = \lambda y$ (9)

Where λ is a given complex constant and $\lambda = \alpha + i\beta$

The application of the single step method to the test problem (9) leads to a first order difference equation of the form $y_{n+1} = R(\lambda h)y_n$ where $R(\lambda h)$ depends on the numerical method. The analytical solution of the test problem (9) gives

$$y(t_{n+1}) = e^{\lambda h} y(t_n)$$

To find the error equation, we have $y_{n+1} = \varepsilon_{n+1} + y(t_{n+1})$

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{n+1} &= R(\lambda h)\varepsilon_n - [e^{\lambda h} - R(\lambda h)y(t_n)] \\ \varepsilon_{n+1} &= R(\lambda h)\varepsilon_n - TE_{n+1} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Where TE_{n+1} is local truncation error and it is independent of ε_n .

The 1st term on the right side of (10) represents the propagation of error from t_n to t_{n+1} and it will be stable if $|R(\lambda h)| \leq 1$ [9].

Definitions

1. Absolute Stability: if $|R(\lambda h)| \leq 1$, $\lambda < 0$, then the single step method is said to be absolutely stable [12].
2. Interval of Absolute Stability: If the method is absolutely stable for all $\lambda h \in (a, b)$ then the interval (a, b) on the real line is said to be the interval of absolute stability [9]
3. Relative Stability: If $R(\lambda h) \leq e^{\lambda h}$, $\lambda > 0$, then the single step method is said to be relatively stable [9].
4. Consider the set $S = \{\mu = \alpha + i\beta, \alpha \leq 0\}$ if $|R(\mu)| \leq 1$ then the method with stability function $R(\mu)$ is called A-stable, where $R(\mu)$ is stability polynomial [9]

A. Stability property of θ -method

To obtain the stability functions of θ -method for solving systems of ODEs apply a linear test equation (9) in the formula of θ -method. The stability function of θ -method for different value of θ is different.

$$\text{If } \theta = 0.5 \text{ (Trapezoidal Rule), } y_n = y_{n-1} + 0.5h[f(t_{n-1}, y_{n-1}) + f(t_n, y_n)]$$

When apply the solution of (15) the stability function is given by

$$y_n = \frac{1+0.5\mu}{1-0.5\mu} y_{n-1}, \quad R_{TR}(\mu) = \frac{1+0.5\mu}{1-0.5\mu} \text{ to be stable } |R_{TR}(\mu)| = \left| \frac{1+0.5\mu}{1-0.5\mu} \right| \leq 1,$$

If $\theta = 1$ (Euler's backward)

$$y_n = y_{n-1} + h[f(t_n, y_n)], \text{ when apply the solution of (15) the stability function is given by}$$

$$R_{BE}(\mu) = \frac{1}{1-\mu} \text{ to be stable } |R_{BE}(\mu)| = \left| \frac{1}{1-\mu} \right| \leq 1$$

Generally for all $\theta \in [0, 1]$, $y_n = y_{n-1} + h[(1-\theta)\lambda y_{n-1} + \theta\lambda y_n]$

When apply in the solution of (9) the stability function gives $R_\theta(\mu) = \frac{1 + (1 - \theta)\mu}{1 - \theta\mu}$, it should be mentioned here that the stability function can be represented as a ratio of two polynomials

$$R(\mu) = \frac{P(\mu)}{Q(\mu)}$$

The stability of the numerical method on the imaginary axis is ensured if $E(\beta) \geq 0$ for all real values of β , where $E(\beta)$ is defined by

$$E(\beta) = Q(i\beta)Q(-i\beta) - P(i\beta)P(-i\beta) \quad [4, 10] \quad (11)$$

B. The effect of Richardson Extrapolation method on stability of θ -method

Is the Richardson extrapolation method stable if the underline method is stable?

The answer to this important question depends on the implementation of the Richardson Extrapolation [4, 10]. This means, for the Passive Richardson Extrapolation the answer is always positive, while for the Active Richardson Extrapolation might become unstable [4]. More precisely, the following theorems can be formulated.

Theorem 1. Assume that the underlying method is either A-stable or L-stable. Assume that the Passive Richardson Extrapolation is used. Then the combined method will be stable when (10) is solved, [4, 10].

Theorem 2. The combined method consisting of the Active Richardson Extrapolation and the Backward Euler Formula is L-stable [4, 10]

Theorem 3. The numerical method consisting of a combination of the Richardson Extrapolation and the θ -method is strongly A-stable when $\theta \in [\theta_0, 1]$ with $\theta_0 = \frac{2}{3}$ [4, 10].

Theorem 4. The computations will in general be unstable when the Trapezoidal Rule is used together with the active Richardson extrapolation [4, 10].

Proof. Since the Trapezoidal Rule is a second-order method, it can be written as

$$y_n = \frac{4w_n - z_n}{3}$$

$$\text{Where } z_n = \left[\frac{1 + 0.5\mu}{1 - 0.5\mu} \right] y_{n-1} \quad \text{and} \quad w_n = \left[\frac{1 + 0.25\mu}{1 - 0.25\mu} \right] y_{n-1}$$

$$\text{Then we have } y_n = \left(\frac{4}{3} \left[\frac{1 + 0.25\mu}{1 - 0.25\mu} \right]^2 - \frac{1}{3} \left[\frac{1 + 0.5\mu}{1 - 0.5\mu} \right] \right) y_{n-1}$$

$$R_{\text{TR+RICH}} = \frac{4}{3} \left[\frac{1 + 0.25\mu}{1 - 0.25\mu} \right]^2 - \frac{1}{3} \left[\frac{1 + 0.5\mu}{1 - 0.5\mu} \right] = \frac{4}{3} \left[\frac{\frac{1}{\mu^2} + \frac{0.5}{\mu} + 0.0625}{\frac{1}{\mu^2} + \frac{0.5}{\mu} + 0.0625} \right] - \frac{1}{3} \left[\frac{\frac{1}{\mu} + 0.5}{\frac{1}{\mu} - 0.5} \right]$$

$$\Rightarrow \lim_{\mu \rightarrow \infty} R_{TR+RICH} = \frac{5}{3} > 1$$

$$|R_{TR+RICH}| = \frac{5}{3} > 1$$

Which means that the computational process will be unstable hence the theorem holds.

Moreover the stability properties of the combined method of Richardson extrapolation with

θ -method for all $\theta \in [0, 1]$ is as follows $z_n = y_{n-1} + h(1-\theta)\lambda y_{n-1} + \theta h\lambda y_n$

Then apply equation (15) which gives $z_n = \frac{(1+(1-\theta)\mu)}{1-\theta\mu} y_{n-1}$ and

$$w_n = \left[\frac{1+(1-\theta)0.5\mu}{1-\theta(0.5)\mu} \right]^2 y_{n-1} \quad (12)$$

Where $\mu = \lambda h$

Then apply Richardson extrapolation leads the following relationship

$$y_n = R(\mu)y_{n-1}, \text{ and}$$

$$R(\mu) = 2 \left[\frac{1+(1-\theta)0.5\mu}{1-\theta(0.5)\mu} \right]^2 - \frac{1+(1-\theta)\mu}{1-\theta\mu}, \text{ for } \theta \neq 0.5 \quad (13)$$

$$\text{To be stable } \left| 2 \left[\frac{1+(1-\theta)0.5\mu}{1-\theta(0.5)\mu} \right]^2 - \frac{1+(1-\theta)\mu}{1-\theta\mu} \right| \leq 1$$

In general the application of the active Richardson Extrapolation on θ -method may cause instability of the computational process.

4. Main results / findings

Many theorems and definitions are stated in the previous part of the paper about stability property of θ -method. However the main finding of this study focused on the stability interval of θ -method on the real and imaginary axis.

Consider the stability function of θ -method $R_\theta(\mu) = \frac{1+(1-\theta)\mu}{1-\theta\mu}$, where $\mu = \alpha + i\beta$

1. In the real axis ($\beta = 0$) the stability function becomes

$$R_\theta(\mu) = \frac{1+(1-\theta)\alpha}{1-\theta\alpha} = 1 + \frac{\alpha}{1-\theta\alpha}$$

$$|R_\theta(\mu)| = \left| 1 + \frac{\alpha}{1-\theta\alpha} \right| \text{ to be stable } |R_\theta(\mu)| = \left| 1 + \frac{\alpha}{1-\theta\alpha} \right| \leq 1$$

$$\text{This is true if } -2 \leq \frac{\alpha}{1-\theta\alpha} \leq 0$$

(14)

To show the stability in the real axis we have three cases; these are the origin, negative real axis and positive real axis. The stability of the method at these three cases is as follows

Case 1. If $\alpha = 0$, then $-2 \leq \frac{\alpha}{1-\theta\alpha} \leq 0$ θ -method is stable on the origin.

Case 2. If $\alpha < 0$ and $1-\theta\alpha > 0$

Multiply equation (14) both sides by $1-\theta\alpha$ gives

$$-2(1-\theta\alpha) < \alpha < 0 \text{ This means } -2(1-\theta\alpha) < \alpha \text{ and } \alpha < 0$$

$$\alpha(2\theta-1) < 2 \text{ and } \alpha < 0 \text{ it is true if } 2\theta-1 \geq 0 \Rightarrow \theta \geq \frac{1}{2}$$

This indicates that θ -method is stable on the negative real axis ($\alpha < 0$) if $\theta \in \left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$

Case 3. If $\alpha > 0$ and $1-\theta\alpha < 0$

Multiply equation (14) both sides by $1-\theta\alpha$ gives

$$-2(1-\theta\alpha) > \alpha > 0 \text{ This means } \alpha(2\theta-1) > 2 \text{ and } \alpha > 0$$

This is true if $2\theta-1 > 0 \Rightarrow \theta > \frac{1}{2}$

$$(2\theta-1) > \frac{2}{\alpha} \text{ and } \alpha > 0$$

$$\theta > \frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow 1 \geq \theta > \frac{1}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{2} \text{ This gives } 2 < \alpha$$

This indicates that θ -method is stable on the positive real axis for $\alpha > 2$ if $\theta \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$

Therefore we can write as a theorem

Theorem 5 : θ -method is stable on the origin and the method is stable on negative real axis ($\alpha < 0$) and for positive the real axis on $2 < \alpha$ for $\theta \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$.

Example 1:- Solve $y' = -3y$, $y(0) = 1$, with $h = 1$

I. For $\theta = 0$ (Euler's forward), $y_{n+1} = y_n + hf(t_n, y_n)$ This implies $y_{n+1} = y_n - 3y_n$

$$\Rightarrow y_{n+1} = -2y_n$$

The formula of Euler's forward method with stability function is given by $y_{n+1} = |1 + \mu| y_n$

$$R_{FE}(\mu) = 1 + \mu \text{ to be stable } |R_{FE}(\mu)| = |1 + \mu| = 2 \not< 1$$

This can't work as $1 < 2$; hence by using Euler's forward method the solution of the given IVP is unstable.

II. For $\theta = 1$ (Euler's backward)

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + hf(t_{n+1}, y_{n+1})$$

$$y_{n+1} = y_n - 3hy_{n+1}$$

The formula of Euler's backward method by stability function is given by

$$y_{n+1} = \left(\frac{1}{1+3h} \right) y_n \text{ this}$$

gives $y_{n+1} = \frac{1}{4} y_n$

$$R_{BE}(\mu) = \frac{1}{1-\mu} \text{ to be stable } |R_{BE}(\mu)| = \left| \frac{1}{1-\mu} \right| \leq 1 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{4} < 1$$

BY using Euler's backward method the solution of the given IVP is stable.

The solution of the given IVP by using two Euler's forward and backward method is as follows in the table bellow

Table 1: Stability property of Euler's forward and backward method

t_{n+1}	y_{n+1} by Euler's forward	y_{n+1} by Euler's backward	Exact value
1	-2	0.25000000	0.04978707
2	4	0.06250000	0.00247875
3	-8	0.00390600	0.00012341
4	16	0.00097650	0.00000614
5	-32	0.00024413	0.00000031
6	64	0.00006103	0.00000002
7	-128	0.00001526	0.00000000
8	256	0.00000381	0.00000000
9	-512	0.00000954	0.00000000
10	1024	0.00000023	0.00000000
11	-2048	0.00000006	0.00000000
12	4090	0.00000001	0.00000000
13	-8192	0.00000000	0.00000000

As we can see from the table the solution of the given IVP by Euler's forward oscillating and rapidly increasing, while by using Euler's backward as $t \rightarrow \infty$ the solution decays to zero (stable).

Let us see the result graphically

Fig 1 (A) Instability of Euler's forward method

The exact solution is $y(t_n) = e^{-3t}$ which decays to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$. However, as we see the above figure if the Euler forward method ($\theta = 0$) is applied to the given equation then the numerical solution is qualitatively wrong, it oscillates and grows but if we use Euler's backward method ($\theta = 1$) the solution decays zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$. This indicates that for $\theta = 0$ the solution is unstable but for $\theta = 1$ the solution of the given ODE is stable.

2. Similarly in the imaginary axis ($\alpha = 0$) we can develop the following theorem

Theorem6: θ - method is stable on the imaginary axis for all $\theta \in [0.5, 1]$ but it is unstable for $\theta \in [0, 0.5)$

Proof:- Consider the stability function $R_\theta(\mu) = \frac{1+i(1-\theta)\beta}{1-i\theta\beta} = 1 + \frac{i\beta}{1-i\theta\beta}$

By rationalizing the denominator, we get

$$R_\theta(\mu) = 1 + \frac{-\theta\beta^2 + i\beta}{1+(\theta\beta)^2},$$

Then by using generalized stability definition we have

$$\begin{aligned} |R_\theta(\mu)| &= \left| 1 + \frac{-\theta\beta^2 + i\beta}{1+(\theta\beta)^2} \right| = \frac{\sqrt{(1+(\theta\beta)^2 - \theta\beta^2)^2 + \beta^2}}{1+(\theta\beta)^2} \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{1+2(\theta\beta)^2 - 2\theta\beta^2 - 2\theta^3\beta^4 + \theta^2\beta^4 + (\theta\beta)^4 + \beta^2}}{1+(\theta\beta)^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{\sqrt{(1+(\theta\beta)^2)^2 - 2\theta\beta^2 - 2\theta^3\beta^4 + \theta^2\beta^4 + \beta^2}}{1+(\theta\beta)^2} \\
&= \sqrt{1 + \frac{-2\theta\beta^2 - 2\theta^3\beta^4 + \theta^2\beta^4 + \beta^2}{(1+(\theta\beta)^2)^2}}
\end{aligned}$$

Suppose the method is stable $\sqrt{1 + \frac{-2\theta\beta^2 - 2\theta^3\beta^4 + \theta^2\beta^4 + \beta^2}{(1+(\theta\beta)^2)^2}} \leq 1$

Square both sides give's $\left| 1 + \frac{-2\theta\beta^2 - 2\theta^3\beta^4 + \theta^2\beta^4 + \beta^2}{(1+(\theta\beta)^2)^2} \right| \leq 1$

This implies $-2 \leq \frac{-2\theta\beta^2 - 2\theta^3\beta^4 + \theta^2\beta^4 + \beta^2}{(1+(\theta\beta)^2)^2} \leq 0$

$$-2 \leq (-2\theta - 2\theta^3\beta^2 + \theta^2\beta^2 + 1)\beta^2 \leq 0$$

This implies that $-2 \leq (1 + \theta^2\beta^2)(1 - 2\theta)\beta^2 \leq 0$ (21)

Case 1. if $(1 - 2\theta) > 0 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{2} > \theta$ the middle term of equation (21) is always positive

$$\left[(1 + \theta^2\beta^2)(1 - 2\theta)\beta^2 > 0 \right] \text{ This is contradiction to our assumption}$$

Therefore if $\frac{1}{2} > \theta$, θ -Method is unstable on the imaginary axis for all $\theta \in [0, 0.5)$.

Case 2. if $(1 - 2\theta) \leq 0 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \leq \theta$ the middle term of equation (21) is always negative

Therefore if $\frac{1}{2} \leq \theta$, θ -Method is stable on the imaginary axis for all $\theta \in [0.5, 1]$.

Alternatively we can use stability formula on the imaginary axis by using equation (17)

Consider $R_\theta(\mu) = \frac{1 + i(1 - \theta)\beta}{1 - i\theta\beta}$, then apply equation (17)

Let $P(\mu) = 1 + i(1 - \theta)\beta$ and $Q(\mu) = 1 - i\theta\beta$

$$P(i\beta) = 1 + i(1 - \theta)\beta, \quad P(-i\beta) = 1 - i(1 - \theta)\beta$$

Then $P(i\beta)P(-i\beta) = 1 + [(1 - \theta)\beta]^2 = 1 + \beta^2 - 2\theta\beta^2 + (\theta\beta)^2$

Similarly $Q(i\beta) = 1 - i\theta\beta, \quad Q(-i\beta) = 1 + i\theta\beta$ then $Q(i\beta)Q(-i\beta) = 1 + (\theta\beta)^2$

$$E(\beta) = Q(i\beta)Q(-i\beta) - P(i\beta)P(-i\beta) = [1 + (\theta\beta)^2] - [1 + \beta^2 - 2\theta\beta^2 + (\theta\beta)^2]$$

$$E(\beta) = 1 + (\theta\beta)^2 - 1 - \beta^2 + 2\theta\beta^2 - (\theta\beta)^2$$

$E(\beta) = (-1 + 2\theta)\beta^2$ this is the stability polynomial for $\theta \in [0, 1]$ in the imaginary axis.

If $\theta \geq 0.5$ then $E(\beta) \geq 0$ otherwise not, the following table shows the result.

Table 2: The stability interval of θ method in the imaginary axis

θ	0	0.10	0.20	0.30	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.70	0.80	0.90	1.00
$-1 + 2\theta$	-1.00	-0.80	-0.60	-0.40	-0.20	0	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00

Let us see the result graphically.

Fig 2: Stability polynomial of THETA method

As we can see in figure 2 the stability polynomial on the imaginary axis deepened on the coefficient of β^2 in $E(\beta)$, hence the values of $-1 + 2\theta \geq 0$ if $\theta \geq 0.5$.

Therefore θ -method is stable on the imaginary axis if $\theta \geq 0.5$ but it is unstable if $\theta < 0.5$

Hence the theorem holds.

5. Conclusion and Future scope

Important properties of Richardson Extrapolations and the effect of Richardson extrapolation on stability was discussed in the previous sections of this study. Some theorems related to the stability of the computational process on the real and imaginary axis have been stated and proved. As discussed above we have tried to realize most of the above objectives. θ -method is stable on the origin and the method is stable on negative real axis ($\alpha < 0$)

and for positive real axis on $2 < \alpha$ for $\theta \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$ and it is stable on the imaginary axis for all $\theta \in [0.5, 1]$

but it is unstable for $\theta \in [0, 0.5)$ Stability region of θ -method outside the real and imaginary axis will be future work.

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